

Fish Borne Parasitic Zoonosis: Major Food Safety Concern

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Abstract

Fish is consumed raw or undercooked, as it is the tradition of most communities. Among many parasites infecting the fish, helminths belonging to the family Anisakidae, Gnathostomidae, Opisthorchiidae, Heterophyidae and Diphyllbothridae are zoonotic in nature. Over half a billion people are at risk of fish-borne helminthiasis around the globe. Intensification of aquaculture, waste disposal, environmental changes, and shorter cooking time increases the risk of zoonotic diseases. Immigration and similar demographic changes like animal transportation, global trading of fish, cultural changes in fish-eating behavior, and stocking of imported fish in new aquatic habitats are linked to new patterns of infection. The control of fish-borne zoonosis needs multidisciplinary and multisectoral participation. It can be achieved by controlled transmission of infections in the reservoir and intermediate hosts, improved fish farming practices, upgraded aquaculture systems to abolish contamination of the ponds, avoiding discard of infected fish or viscera, environmental sanitation, and mass chemotherapy of people at risk in endemic areas. It is advisable to avoid the consumption of raw, undercooked, and poorly prepared dried or pickled fish. Global food standards advocate the physical removal of parasites and freezing raw, pickled, or cured fish.

However, these practices do not put an end to parasites completely, which is uneconomical and unaccepted by consumers. The intricacy of diagnosis, complicated human cultural behaviors, and incomprehension of potential economic costs have made this field scientifically dubious and unappealing to researchers. There is room for researchers to

develop specific molecular or immunological methods to aid diagnosis. Morphological identification needs to be made by molecular approaches like molecular markers, genetic markers, phylogenetic analysis to solve the long due misunderstandings of the host associations and host ranges for several species of fish helminths, wrong taxonomy, and distribution.

Keywords: Fish parasites, Helminths, Foodborne Zoonosis